

ADHESIVE STRAIN MEASUREMENT IN PATCH REPAIRED CFRP LAMINATE USING 2D DIC

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Abstract

In the present work, an experimental and numerical study is carried out to analyze the behaviour of adhesively bonded joints in symmetrical patch repaired CFRP laminate under tensile load. In first part of the experimental study, digital image correlation (DIC) technique is employed for material characterization of adhesive and composite as per ASTM standard and they are used in numerical simulation. In second part, same technique is used to analyze the strain field distribution developed in existing adhesive layer between composite panel and patch. High peel and shear strain develops near the overlap end which eventually lead to debonding of patch are analyzed using 2D DIC. Two different kind of adhesive materials are considered in this study. The effect of nature of adhesive and patch edge tapering on strain distribution in the adhesive layer is also closely examined. The failure mechanism is also studied. Finally, the experimental results are compared with the numerical predictions and they compare good.

1 Introduction

Joints are common in many structural applications especially in automobile, aerospace and shipbuilding industries because of the need for assembly, disassembly, inspection, repair etc. Adhesively bonded joints has rapidly increased its application in these sectors because it offers significant advantages over the mechanically fastened joints like light weight, minimal source of stress concentrations and efficient load transfer from one adherend to another. Despite various advantages, joints constitute the weakest link in adhesively bonded structures and in most of the cases failure initiates from the joints. A considerable amount of research has been carried out

to understand the behavior of adhesively bonded joints. Moutrille et al. [1] have studied the shear strain field in an adhesive joint between composite patch and aluminium. They have used DIC technique to obtain the displacement field through the thickness of patched specimen subjected to tensile load and then shear strain fields are obtained from the displacement fields. Haghani et al. [2] have investigated experimentally the effect of geometrical modifications like laminate end tapering or adding adhesive filler on strain distribution in adhesive joint between CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastic) laminate and steel using DIC technique. Ruiz et al. [3] conducted experimental and numerical study to assess the strain distribution adhesive layer of epoxy bonded aluminium-aluminium and aluminium-CFRP double lap shear joints under tensile loading. They have used high magnification moiré interferometry technique for experimental study and the obtained results are compared with numerical prediction. Shih-Chuan and Shou-Jen [4] presented an analytical solution to predict the load transfer and shear stress distribution in adhesively bonded region of double-sided patch joint under static tensile loadings. The obtained results are compared with the finite element results. Colavito et al. [5] have used DIC technique to measure the strain distribution in adhesively bonded composite lap joint. Wang et al. [6] have presented the results of a combined experimental and finite element investigation on strain/stress distributions around the overlap ends of laminated composite single-lap joints. Crammond et al. [7] have used novel full-field measurement techniques to analyze the complex stress and strain distributions in adhesively bonded composite joints using thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) and DIC.

Most of the works have been done on adhesive joints between metal (like steel, aluminium) and composites. Off late focus is on composite/composite adhesive joints. However, due to increasing demand of light weight and high strength structures, high performance composites like CFRP are extensively used in various domains involving adhesively bonded composite joints. Especially in aircrafts lot of composite applications has come into the fore. The adhesively bonded composite joints is also emerged as a potential means of repairing the damaged composite parts for attaining high structural efficiency and improved fatigue life. However, no significant experimental work has been reported on behaviour of adhesive layer in patch repaired CFRP laminates. To improve the performance of bonded repair of composite structures, it is essential to understand the strength, stress/strain distribution and failure mechanism of adhesively bonded joints between composite adherends.

In present work, the behaviour of adhesively bonded joints in double sided patch repaired CFRP laminate under tensile load is investigated experimentally using DIC technique. The material properties of adhesive and composite are obtained using non-contact 3D-DIC technique. The whole field strain distribution in adhesive layer as well as high peeling and shear strain near overlap end is analyzed using 2D-DIC technique. The influence of adhesive nature as well as patch edge tapering on strain distribution in adhesive layer is investigated. The experimental results are compared with the numerical predictions and they are found to be in good agreement.

2 Materials and specimen fabrication

In this study, two different types of adhesive materials i.e. a very brittle adhesive namely Araldite AV138/HV998 and an intermediate adhesive Araldite 2011 are used. Both are two-part epoxy based adhesive manufactured by Huntsman. The composite laminates are made of unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy sheet. The carbon fiber is manufactured by Hindustan Technical Fabrics Ltd. India, having a weight of 230 gsm. The matrix is made from epoxy resin LY556 mixed with hardener HY951 supplied by Huntsman. The fabrication of various types of specimens is discussed in the next sub-section.

2.1 Specimen for adhesive properties evaluation

The material properties of adhesives are determined as per ASTM D-638 standard [8]. The specimen dimensions are shown in Fig. 1. The specimens are fabricated in split molds made of aluminium as shown in Fig. 2(a). The aluminium mold is prepared with wire EDM (Electrical Discharge Machining) and then cleaned with acetone. The mold is placed on a flat Perspex sheet and a release agent (wax) is applied on interior surface of the mold to enable easy separation of cured adhesive. The resin (AV138) and hardener (HV998) is taken in the ratio of 10:4 by weight and mixed thoroughly. The resin-hardener mixture is poured into mold and then allowed for curing at room temperature. Araldite 2011 mixture supplied in tubes is poured into mold by using applicator gun recommended by supplier (Huntsman) and it is also cured at room temperature. The cured adhesive is shown in Fig. 2(b) & (c).

2.2 Specimen for composite properties evaluation

The composite laminates are fabricated by hand layup technique. The resin (LY556) and hardener (HY951) are taken in the ratio of 10:1 by weight. The resin-hardener mixture is poured in-between the successive layer of carbon fiber mat and then spread using roller. The number of layers based on required thickness is placed and finally the entire laminate is rolled to remove excess resin, entrapped air. The composite laminate is allowed to cure at room temperature for twenty four hours. Specimens are cut from fabricated laminates to over dimension (about 3-5 mm on each side) using abrasive cut-off wheel mounted on hand-held saw. Specimens are then accurately machined to the required dimension by a milling machine fitted with a special diamond coated end mills (JS520100D3S.0Z6-SIRA) supplied by SECO-Jabro Tools. Beveled Aluminium tabs of required dimension are bonded to the test specimen ends using AV138/HV998 adhesive material. Before bonding the tabs, bonding surface of the tabs and specimens are roughened using 200-grit sandpaper and then cleaned with isopropyl alcohol. The in-plane material properties of CFRP composite laminate are determined as per ASTM standards. Tensile tests are performed as per ASTM D-3039 standard [9] to evaluate longitudinal and transverse properties. Shear tests are performed as

per ASTM D-3518 standard [10] to evaluate in-plane shear modulus.

2.3 Specimen configuration for adhesive strain measurement

The typical model for the repaired panel is shown in Fig. 3. Both patch and panel are made of unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy composite laminate and fabricated by hand layup technique as explained in sub-section 2.2. The length (L), width (W) and the thickness (t) of the panel are 250 mm, 50 mm and 1.6 mm respectively. The stacking sequence in the panel is $[0^\circ]_4$. A circular hole of 10 mm diameter (d) is drilled at the center of the panel by using diamond coated drill bit supplied by SECO-Jabro Tools. The hole is drilled to simulate the effect of damage removal as it happens in the case of low velocity impact damage. The panel with open hole is repaired with adhesively bonded double sided rectangular patch having stacking sequence of $[0^\circ]_3$. The length (L_p), width (W_p) and thickness (t_p) of the patch are 60 mm, 50 mm and 1.2 mm respectively. Patch is bonded over the damaged area of panel using an adhesive of thickness t_a and then it is allowed to cure at room temperature. Before bonding the patch, bonding surfaces are prepared carefully as explained earlier. After bonding the patch, weight is placed over the patch area to remove the entrapped air, excessive adhesive as well as to obtain the uniform adhesive thickness. The excess adhesive is cleaned with isopropyl alcohol. Similar bonding procedure is followed for all the test specimens to obtain similar adhesive thickness. Beveled aluminium tabs of dimension 50 mm x 50 mm x 2 mm are bonded at each end of the specimen for gripping purpose.

3 Experimental setup and test procedure

The experimental setup used in present study is shown in Fig 4. It consists of a 2D DIC system and computer-controlled MTS Landmark[®] servo-hydraulic cyclic test machine of 100 kN capacity. The 2D DIC setup consists of an 8-bit Grasshopper[®] CCD Camera (POINTGREY- GRAS-50S5M-C) having a spatial resolution of 2448 x 2048 pixels, coupled with Schneider Xenoplan lenses of 35 mm focal length. The camera is mounted on a tripod having inbuilt spirit level to ensure horizontal level. The DIC system is from Correlated Solutions Inc. Prior to the testing, random speckle patterns are made over the specimen surface by spraying carbon

black/titanium white colors with an airbrush having a nozzle of 0.5 mm diameter.

3.1 Test procedure for adhesive and composite properties evaluation

The detailed test procedure for in-plane properties evaluation of CFRP composite laminate using 3D DIC technique is elaborately explained in Ref. [11]. The adhesive properties are also determined by 3D DIC technique. All tests for material characterization are performed in displacement controlled mode and the testing speeds are specified in accordance with ASTM standards. Firstly, the adhesive specimens are tested at a tensile loading rate of 3.75 mm/min and 15 images per second are grabbed to obtain more data points for smooth experimental plot. The composite specimens are tested at a loading rate varying from 1-2 mm/min as per the ASTM standards and 10 images per second are grabbed. The load and displacement data for each image being grabbed is also recorded using data acquisition system during each test. An axial extensometer of 20 mm gauge length is also attached in center of the specimen to enable a comparison between the in-plane properties obtained from DIC technique and extensometer.

3.2 Test procedure for adhesive strain measurement

The strain measurement along the thickness of adhesive layer between patch/panel interface is obtained using 2D DIC technique. As the layer thickness is very small, CCD camera is coupled with InfiniProbe TS-160 (from Infinity Photo-Optical Company) thereby by providing a magnification range of 0-16X. To obtain a good field of view proper illumination is achieved with two white LED (30W) lamps provided with illumination controller. The specimen is fixed in hydraulic grips and camera is aligned perpendicular to ZOI (zone of interest). The ZOI near the patch edge (see Fig. 3(b)) is zoomed in and tensile testing is performed at a loading rate of 1 mm/min and 10 images per second are grabbed. Using data acquisition card, load and displacement value are simultaneously recorded when images are being grabbed.

4 Finite element modeling and analysis

A linear static 3-D finite element analysis of repaired panel is carried out using ANSYS 13

software. The geometry and dimensions of panel and patch are kept same as that of experimental model. The mesh pattern around the hole and patch edge is kept very fine to capture the high stress gradient around it. Around the circular hole there are 15360 elements (96 circumferential; 40 radial; 4 thickness). Every layer is meshed with one element in thickness direction for both patch and panel. In thickness direction, the panel is meshed with four elements, adhesive with ten elements and patch with three elements. The model is built with 20-noded solid 186 brick element. The patch is bonded to the panel above the hole using adhesive material. Multi point constraint (MPC) algorithm is employed for ensuring a perfect bonding between patch/panel and panel/adhesive. The elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of adhesive(s) used in this analysis are obtained experimentally as presented in section 5.1. Fibers in the panel and patch are aligned parallel to the loading direction. The panel is fixed at bottom face and an in-plane tensile load of 13.5 kN is applied at the top face along x -direction so as to simulate the experimental boundary conditions. The results obtained from FEA are compared with the experimental data for the same load. The zoomed view of finite element model of the repaired panel is shown in the Fig. 5.

5 Results and discussions

5.1 Material properties of adhesives and CFRP composite laminate

The material properties of adhesives and CFRP composite laminate (adherend) used in the present work are determined using 3D DIC technique. The area within the gauge length (20 mm) of extensometer is selected as region of interest (ROI) towards post-processing. The spatial resolution of ROI for Araldite AV138/HV998 adhesive is 14.6 pixels/mm. A subset size of 29 x 29 pixels is chosen along with a step size of 7 pixels for performing DIC calculations. The stress – strain curve for both the adhesives obtained from DIC technique and extensometer is shown in Fig. 6. It can be observed from the figure that the modulus value predicted by DIC technique is closely matching with the extensometer data. The error between the DIC and extensometer value is 0.5 % in case of Araldite AV138/HV998 adhesive and it is 1.9 % for Araldite 2011 adhesive. The summary of material properties

of adhesives and CFRP composite laminate obtained from DIC technique are presented in Table 1.

5.2 Adhesive thickness measurement

The adhesive thickness is measured by an optical microscope (Olympus STM6) using objective lens (Olympus MPLFLN 10x / 0.30) at a magnification of 10x. Figure 7 shows an image taken from optical microscope to evaluate the adhesive thickness in repaired panel. The measurement is taken at different locations and the average value is reported. The adhesive thickness for a panel repaired with Araldite AV138/HV998 and Araldite 2011 adhesive are 0.2 mm and 0.21 mm respectively.

5.3 Strain distribution in adhesive layer

5.3.1 Araldite 2011 adhesive

The peel (ϵ_{xx}) and shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) distribution in adhesive layer of double sided bonded notched panel (with hole) at a load of 13.35 kN is shown in Fig. 8. The ROI for correlation corresponds to a zone of 4.24 mm x 4.36 mm respectively. The spatial resolution is 417.5 pixel /mm. A subset size of 41 x 41 pixels with a step size of 7 pixels is chosen for correlation. It can be observed from the figure that the high peel strain exist near overlap edge of the patch from which the damage would initiate leading to patch debonding from this location. It can also be observed from the figures that the maximum shear strain concentration also occurs nearer to overlap edge of the patch at patch/adhesive and adhesive/panel interface in the adhesive layer. This is due to the load transfer happening between the patch and panel across the adhesive layer. It can also be observed from the figure that the shear strain contour plot in both the adhesive layer (both left and right side of the panel) are smooth and similar, but they are reversed. The shear strain is positive in right side adhesive and negative in left side one. Figure 9 shows a comparison between peel and shear strain variation along the thickness of adhesive layer near the patch overlap edge. One can observe that the magnitude of shear strain is more as compared to the peel strain. The variation of peeling strain (ϵ_{xx}) at mid-thickness of adhesive layer along the bondline (joint length) is shown in Fig. 10. It can be observed from the figure that the high peel strain exist near the overlap end (adhesive edge) and it starts reducing as one moves away from the free end along

the bondline. Similar observation is also made in Ref. [2]. The failure mechanism in the repaired panel is shown in Fig. 11. The damage initiated at the patch/adhesive interface near the patch overlap edge as expected and then swiftly propagated towards the adhesive/panel interface followed by the progressive patch debonding over the interface area.

5.3.2 Araldite AV138/HV998 adhesive

The whole field strain distribution in adhesive layer for a double sided bonded notched panel is shown Fig. 12. The spatial resolution is 468.8 pixel /mm. A subset size of 41 x 41 pixels with a step size of 7 pixels is chosen for correlation. It is found that a high peel strain develops near the patch overlap edge at patch/adhesive and adhesive/panel interface as observed in Araldite 2011 system. However, the shear strain distribution in AV138/HV998 adhesive layer is found to be more localized and scattered as compared to the Araldite 2011 system (see Fig. 8(b) & 12(b)). A comparative plot between Araldite 2011 and AV138/HV998 adhesive system in terms of shear strain variation in the adhesive layer is shown in Fig. 13. One can also observe from figure that the magnitude of shear strain is more in Araldite 2011 adhesive layer as compared to that of the AV138/HV998 system. This is due to the fact that the Araldite 2011 is ductile in nature and offer more elongation and hence more strain as compared to brittle grade Araldite AV138/HV998 system. The damage progression in the repaired panel repaired having Araldite AV138/HV998 system is shown in the Fig. 14. It is clear from the peel strain contour plot (see Fig. 14(a)) that the debonding of the patch initiated near the patch/adhesive interface and then propagated along the interface. The damage then propagates towards the adhesive/panel interface followed by the patch debonding along this interface.

5.3.3 Effect of patch edge tapering

The influence of patch edge tapering is investigated for the case of panel repaired with double sided patch using Araldite 2011 system. The chamfered length or length of tapered edge is 2.3 mm. Figure 15 shows the peel and shear strain distribution in the adhesive layer for a panel repaired with tapered patches. It is found that the high strain concentration exist in the adhesive layer near the patch overlap edge at patch/adhesive and also adhesive/panel

interface quite similar to the observation made in section 5.3.1. Figure 16 shows a comparative plot of shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) in the adhesive layer (Araldite 2011) for the panel repaired with double sided straight edge and tapered edge patch at a tensile load of 13.5 kN. The line considered for the plot is also shown there. It is clear from the figure that the edge tapering in the patch reduces the peak strain in the adhesive layer as compared to the panel repaired with straight edge patch.

5.4 Numerical results

In this section the results obtained from finite element analysis (FEA) for a panel repaired with double sided patch using Araldite 2011 system is presented and also compared with DIC results.

Figure 17 shows the strain distribution in the adhesive layer (Araldite 2011) obtained from FEA at a load of 13.5 kN. The FEA results are presented with adjusted scale to match against DIC scale. It can be observed from the figure that a high peel and shear strain concentration exist near the patch overlap edge at patch/adhesive interface. The strain distribution obtained from FEA is found to be consistent with experimental observation presented in section 5.3.1 (see Fig. 8).

A comparative plot between DIC and FEA result in terms of shear strain variation along the thickness of the repaired configuration at a load of 13.5 kN is shown in Fig. 18. The line considered for the plot is also shown in the figure. It can be observed from the plot that the shear strain is very low in the patch and panel zone whereas it peaks up at the center of the adhesive layer. It is also clear from the figure that a good correlation exist between the DIC and FEA result.

Figure 19 shows a comparative plot between DIC and FEA results in terms of shear strain variation at mid-thickness of the adhesive (Araldite 2011) layer along the joint length (bondline). The line considered for the comparative plot is also shown in the figure. It can be observed from the figure that the shear strain is maximum near the adhesive end and it reduces as one moves away from the adhesive end along the bondline or length of the joint. Similar observation has been made in Ref. [1]. Besides small difference in magnitude, ϵ_{xy} variation

from both DIC and FEA has a similar trend and relatively shows a good agreement.

6 Conclusions

In the present work, an experimental and numerical study is carried out to understand the behaviour of adhesive layer in a symmetrical patch repaired CFRP laminate under tensile load using DIC. It is found that the DIC is suitable for estimating the localized and global strain distribution over small but critical locations from which the damage would initiate. Initially, the same DIC technique is employed for material property evaluation of adhesive and composite laminate by conducting a series of tests as per ASTM standard. The same properties are used for FEA simulations. Later, the strain distribution in adhesive layer is analysed using 2D-DIC. It is found that a high peel and shear strain concentration exist near the patch overlap edge (joint location) at patch/adhesive and adhesive/panel interface. The influence of nature of adhesive on strain distribution in the adhesive layer is also investigated experimentally. It is found that strain distribution in adhesive layer in case of brittle adhesive (Araldite AV138/HV998) is more localized and scattered as compared to ductile one like Araldite 2011. Also, the Araldite 2011 adhesive presents more peel and shear strain in adhesive layer as compared to AV138/HV998 adhesive system. It is also found that the edge tapering of the patch reduces the peak strain in the adhesive layer of a repaired configuration in contrast to the straight edge patch. It is also observed that the failure in repaired configuration initiated from overlap edge as expected, leading to debonding of the patch from this location. Finally, a finite element based study is carried out to get the whole field strain distribution in the adhesive layer. The FEA prediction is compared with the DIC results and they are found to be in good agreement.

Fig. 1. Specimen dimensions of adhesive as per ASTM D-638 standard

Fig. 2. Adhesive specimen casting (a) split aluminium mold (b) Araldite AV138 / HV998 specimen (c) Araldite 2011 specimen

Fig. 3. Specimen geometry (a) front view of patched panel (b) side view of double sided repaired panel

Fig. 4. Experimental Setup

Fig. 5. Finite element model

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Comparative plot of stress – strain curve obtained from DIC and extensometer (a) Araldite 2011 (b) Araldite AV138/HV998

Fig. 7. Adhesive thickness measured using optical microscope at a magnification of 10x (a) Araldite AV138/HV998 (b) Araldite 2011

Fig. 8. Whole field strain distribution in adhesive layer for a double sided patched panel at a tensile load of 13.5 kN (Araldite 2011) (a) peel strain - ϵ_{xx} (b) shear strain - ϵ_{xy}

Fig. 9. Comparison between peel and shear strain variation in the adhesive layer (Araldite 2011)

Fig. 10. Variation of peel strain in adhesive layer (Araldite 2011)

Fig. 11. Failure mechanism in case of double sided patched panel (Araldite 2011)

Fig. 12. Whole field strain distribution in the adhesive layer for a double sided patched panel at a tensile load of 13.5 kN (AV138/HV998) (a) peel strain - ϵ_{xx} (b) shear strain - ϵ_{xy}

Fig. 13. Comparative plot of shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) in adhesive layer for the panel repaired with Araldite 2011 and AV138/HV998 adhesive systems

Fig. 14. Damage progression at 24.45 kN (a) peel strain - ϵ_{xx} (b) damage path

Fig. 15. Whole field strain distribution in the adhesive layer for a panel repaired with tapered patches at a tensile load of 13.5 kN (Araldite 2011) (a) peel strain - ϵ_{xx} (b) shear strain - ϵ_{xy}

Fig. 16. Comparative plot of shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) for the panel repaired with straight edge and tapered edge double sided patch using Araldite 2011 adhesive

Fig. 17. Whole field strain distribution in Araldite 2011 adhesive layer of double sided patched panel at a tensile load of 13.5 kN (a) peel strain - ϵ_{xx} (b) shear strain - ϵ_{xy}

Fig. 18. Comparison of shear strain variation between DIC and FEA

Fig. 19. Comparison of shear strain variation along the joint length between DIC and FEA

Table 1: Material properties of CFRP laminate and adhesives obtained using DIC technique

CFRP Composite Laminate	
Longitudinal modulus, E_{xx} (GPa)	84.16
Transverse modulus, $E_{yy} = E_{zz}$ (GPa)	7.12
Shear moduli, $G_{xy} = G_{xz}$ (GPa)	3.30
Shear modulus, G_{yz} (GPa) *	2.47
Poisson's ratio ($\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz}$)	0.31
Poisson's ratio (ν_{yz}) *	0.43
Araldite AV138/HV998 Adhesive	
Young's modulus E (GPa)	4.13
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.41
Araldite 2011 Adhesive	
Young's modulus E (GPa)	1.86
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.38

*Out-plane properties are evaluated using the procedure given in Ref. [12]

References

- [1] M.-P. Moutrille, K. Derrien, D. Baptiste, X. Balandraud and M. Grédiac "Through-thickness strain field measurement in a composite/aluminium adhesive joint". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 40, pp 985–996, 2009.
- [2] R. Haghani, M. Al-Emrani and R. Kliger "Effects of geometrical modifications on behaviour of adhesive joints used to bond CFRP laminates to steel members – experimental investigation". *Proceedings of the nordic steel construction conference (NSCC)*, Malmo, Sweden, 2009.
- [3] P. D. Ruiz, F. Jumbo, J. M. Huntley, I. A. Ashcroft and G. M. Swallowe "Experimental and numerical investigation of strain distributions within the adhesive layer in bonded joints". *Strain*, 47, pp. 88–104, 2011.
- [4] H. Shiu-Chuan and L. Shou-Jen "Load transfer in adhesive double-sided patch joints". *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, pp 1–13, 2012.
- [5] K.W. Colavito, M. Das, J. Gorma and E. Madenci "Digital image correlation of adhesive strains in bonded composite lap joints". *Proceedings of the 49th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC structures, structural dynamics, and materials conference*. Schaumburg, Illinois, p 1816, 2008.
- [6] Z.Y. Wang, L. Wang, W. Guo, H. Deng, J.W. Tong and F. Aymerich "An investigation on strain/stress distribution around the overlap end of laminated composite single-lap joints". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 89, pp 589–595, 2009.
- [7] G. Crammond, S. W. Boyd and J. M. Dulieu-Barton "Through-thickness load transfer in adhesively bonded composite joints". *Conference Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Mechanics Series*, pp 111–114, 2013.
- [8] Standard test method for tensile properties of plastics, *ASTM D-638*.
- [9] Standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials, *ASTM D3039/D 3039M-00*.
- [10] Standard test method for in-plane shear response of polymer matrix composite materials by test of a ± 45 laminate, *ASTM D3518*.
- [11] M. Kashfuddoja and M. Ramji "Whole-field strain analysis and damage assessment of adhesively bonded patch repair of CFRP laminates using 3D-DIC and FEA". *Composites: Part B*, 53, pp 46–61, 2013.
- [12] P. Mallick "*Fiber Reinforced Composites: Materials, Manufacturing, and Design*". 3rd Edition, CRC Press, 2007.